

Notes on the silver vlei spider *Leucauge festiva* (Blackwall, 1866) from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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Abstract: *Leucauge festiva* (Blackwall, 1866) is an African endemic described from Equatorial Africa. Little is known about their behaviour and notes are provided on their general morphology and distribution in South Africa with photographs on their webs and lifestyle.

Key words: South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), Free State, web building.

INTRODUCTION

Leucauge White, 1841 is represented by 167 species with eight species known from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021). The species *Leucauge festiva* (Blackwall, 1866) is an African endemic described from equatorial Africa as *Tetragnatha festiva* (World Spider Catalog, 2021). They are brightly coloured and make orb webs in low vegetation. The aim of this paper is to add notes on the morphology of *L. festiva* based on images of living spiders, their behaviour and distribution.

METHODS

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), requests were made for photographs of species for the SANSa Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012). Most of the observations were made by the second author (AJ) in grassland at the Mpetsane Conservation Estate (MCE) that is situated in the Eastern Free State highlands some 14 km from Clocolan. The MCE (28°48'S; 27°39'E) covers 164 ha and it is a registered conservancy (Amohela-ho-Spitskop) sanctuary and nature reserve. Several sets of photographs of *Leucauge* spp. have been received from the public. In several instances, the specimens were also sampled and the voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) of the Agricultural Research Council Plant Health and Protection division.

TAXONOMY

Leucauge festiva (Blackwall, 1866)

Tetragnatha festiva Blackwall, 1866: 467.

Meta splendida Butler, 1883: 765, pl. 57, f. 3.

Leucauge festiva Tullgren, 1910: 153, pl. 3, f. 76; Wiehle, 1967: 193, f. 41.

Diagnostic characteristics: The species is recognised by the double fringe of trichobothria on the prolateral surface of the basal half of the posterior femora – a character present in all *Leucauge* species (Fig. 3). Size: TL 8-9 mm (males little smaller than females. Carapace is shiny yellow-brown; rounded in front and on the sides, slightly convex, with a large indentation in the medial line of the posterior region (Fig. 1); eyes on black spots on the anterior part of the cephalothorax; four median eyes nearly form a square; chelicerae short and thick and with strong projecting spurs, which are greatly enlarged in males (Fig. 9). Abdomen silvery, decorated with reddish mask with tints of maroon, yellow, gold and green, with distinct black spots on anterior and posterior end (Figs 4-5); abdomen elongate, sub-cylindrical with short posterior tip; ventrally with broad medial band varies from green to brown; bordered by thin white to yellow bands (Fig. 6). Legs are yellowish brown; long and slender with three claws, with many spines, posterior femora with double fringe of trichobothria. Male and female genitalia relatively simple; male embolus enclosed or coiled together with conductor (Fig. 8); female epigyne with fingerlike scape (Fig. 7).

Figures 1-5. *Leucauge festiva*. 1. Female dorsal view; 2. Male lateral view; 3. Leg 4 femur with trichobothria; 4. Abdomen of female; 5. Abdomen of male. Photo credits 1-2 Peter Webb 3. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman 4-5. Allen Jones

Figures 6-9. *Leucauge festiva*: 6. Female abdomen ventral view; 7. Female epigyne dorsal view (C. Haddad); 8. Male palp (C. Haddad); 9. Male chelicerae ventral view (Ansie Dippenaar-Sxchoeman).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Eswatini (NCA), Ethiopia (Blackwall, 1866), Equatorial Africa (Blackwall, 1866), Namibia (Griffin & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1991), South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010), Tanzania (Tullgren, 1910), Kenya (Kioko *et al.*, 2021), Madagascar (Butler, 1883).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

As part of the SANSA, large numbers of specimens were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). They have been sampled from all provinces but there is only one record from the Northern Cape. They are abundant in the Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad, 2014) and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013) but absent from more arid regions. The species was also sampled from avocado and macadamia orchards, as well as pumpkin and tomato fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013). The species is protected in >10 reserves (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Due to the species' wide range, its International Union for Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (IUCN) status is Least Concern.

COMMON NAMES

Species known as the masked silver vlei spider; red, gold and silver vlei spider and silver vlei spider.

BEHAVIOUR

Web construction: A common species at MCE that makes large symmetrical orb webs about 500-600 mm in diameter. They are almost always placed between long grass stalks, rarely between plant stalks, about 300-400 mm above the ground, so ideally positioned to catch grasshoppers – their usual prey. The inclination of the webs varies from vertical (Fig. 11) to horizontal (Fig. 12), and is often at an angle to the substrate (Fig. 13). The webs are left standing for days until the spider moves off to begin again at a new site. Old webs are abandoned and disintegrate naturally.

At MCE they do not necessarily live near water and are found in mountain grassland at 1 750-1 850 m above sea level. They often get frosted and misted at night. They only really appear in late sum-

Figures 10-14. *Leucauge festiva*: 10. Female on open hub of web; 11. Female in complete vertical web at night; 12. Female in web made in grass with horizontal inclination; 13. Female in web with slight inclination; 14. Female in open hub early in the morning. Photo credits 10-14 Allen Jones.

Figures 15-17. *Leucauge festiva*: Close-ups of webs to show the variation in web structure. Photo credit A. Jones.

The webs are large with an open hub in the middle. There is an open area between the hub and the sticky spirals that contains only radii. A typical *L. festiva* web contains 33-37 radii and the capture viscid part contains 35-38 spirals. When the web is horizontal the spider is found on the underside of the hub (Fig. 18). Sometimes two to three spiders share a web and do not seem to compete for space.

Figure 18 *Leucauge festiva* on horizontal web. Photo credit J. van Zyl.

Figure 19. *Leucauge festiva* mating. Photo: H. de Klerk.

Mating and egg sacs: The male is smaller than the female and takes up a position parallel with her body during mating. Levi (1980) described an egg sac of *L. venusta* from Virginia constructed of fluffy orange-white silk, measuring approximately 8-9 mm in diameter, and containing several hundred eggs. The eggs were reddish-orange and approximately 0.4 mm in diameter. The egg sac is commonly attached to a leaf or twig near the edge of the web. They moult while hanging from the hub of the web, and the shed exuviae often remain in the web for a period of time.

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